

1 Thermal- and Light-Induced Evolution of the 2D/3D 2 Interface in Lead-Halide Perovskite Films

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13 14 15 **Abstract**

16 The instability of halide perovskites towards moisture is one of the main challenge in the field that
17 needs to be overcome to successfully integrate these materials in commercially viable
18 technologies. One of the most popular way to ensure device stability is to form 2D/3D interfaces

19 by using bulky organic molecules on top of the 3D perovskite thin film. Despite its promise, it is
20 unclear whether this approach is able to avoid 3D bulk degradation under accelerated aging
21 conditions, i.e. thermal stress and light soaking. In this regard, it is crucial to know whether the
22 interface is structurally and electronically stable or not. In this work, we use the bulky
23 phenethylammonium cation (PEA^+) to form 2D layers on top of 3D single- and triple-cation halide
24 perovskite films. The dynamical change of the 2D/3D interface is monitored under thermal stress
25 and light soaking by in situ photoluminescence. We find that in pristine conditions the large
26 organic cation diffuses only in 3D perovskite thin films of poor structural stability, i.e. single-
27 cation MAPbI_3 . The same diffusion, together with a dynamical change of the crystalline structure
28 of the 2D/3D interface, are observed even on high quality 3D films, i.e. triple-cation MAFACsPbI_3 ,
29 upon thermal stress at 85°C and light soaking. Importantly, in such conditions, the resistance of
30 the thin film to moisture is lost.

31 **KEYWORDS:** 2D/3D Perovskites, Phenethylammonium Ion, Photoluminescence, Thermal stress.

32

33 Introduction

34 Perovskite solar cells (PSC) are among the most promising emergent photovoltaic technologies.

35 Solution-processed devices have now reached power conversion efficiencies (PCE) higher than

36 25%¹ and 18%^{2,3} on small cells and mini-modules, respectively. Despite the great promise and

37 strengths of PSCs, some concerns regarding their long-term stability under real-world conditions

38 still hold the technology back from its commercialisation.⁴ Therefore, most recent works have

39 focused on understanding degradation mechanisms occurring in PSCs to improve their stability.

40 Halide perovskites, in their 3D form have a ABX_3 crystal structure, where A is an

41 organic/inorganic cation (for example, methylammonium MA^+ , formamidinium FA^+ or Cs^+), B is

42 a metal cation (Pb^{2+} or Sn^{2+}) and X is a halide (Cl^- , Br^- or I^-).⁵ Alternative to 3D perovskites,

43 2D perovskites with the so-called Ruddlesden–Popper structure $\text{R}_2\text{A}_{n-1}\text{B}_n\text{X}_{3n+1}$ have been

44 studied, where R is a bulky organic cation that acts as a spacer between the inorganic sheets and
45 n indicates the number of inorganic layers held together.⁶ They show wider bandgaps and higher
46 exciton binding energies, which reduce the light absorption spectra and hinder the separation of
47 carriers, respectively. As a consequence, they generally present lower PCEs than 3D perovskite
48 when embodied in solar cells.⁷ Nevertheless, one of the most studied approach to improve the
49 stability of PSCs consists of combining 3D perovskites with 2D structures, by forming either a
50 layered structure, where 3D frameworks are sliced into well-defined 2D layers,⁸⁻¹⁰ or a multi-
51 junction stack where the 2D perovskite is formed only on the top-surface of a 3D perovskite
52 film.^{11,12} One-step and layer-by-layer growth techniques have been shown, where the organic
53 bulky spacer is either directly blended within the perovskite precursor solution or deposited over
54 the bulk 3D perovskite layer, respectively. Both approaches showed that the low-dimensional
55 perovskite layer self-assembles as a thin capping layer on the top of the bulk 3D perovskite.¹³ It
56 was demonstrated that such thin film does not only hinder moisture uptake, but it can also act as
57 selective charge extraction layer, reducing the recombination of photo-generated carriers at the
58 interface, enhancing charge-transfer kinetics and inhibiting the volatilization of
59 methylammonium.¹⁴⁻²⁰ To date, the highest efficiency reported for 2D/3D junction absorbers is
60 23.32%, where a phenethylammonium (PEA) salt solution is spin coated onto a FAPbI₃
61 perovskite film.¹²

62 Given the great advances in engineering multi-junction structural perovskite absorbers, complete
63 understanding of the 3D/2D interface evolution under external stressors like heat, illumination
64 and continuous biasing is needed for considering this solution in real life applications. For
65 example, it is not clear whether the 2D perovskite layer is stable on the surface without
66 undergoing structural transformation. Indeed, most of the stability tests reported in the literature

67 for 3D/2D multi-junction PSCs have been measured either on encapsulated devices or in inert
68 atmosphere at room temperature, while internationally recognized qualification standards require
69 the solar cell to be aged at 85°C under continuous maximum power point tracking at 1 Sun
70 illumination.²¹ Liu et al recently showed that the PCE of MAPbI₃ solar cells capped with 2D
71 BA₂Pb₂I₆ thin films dropped by 40% after only 125 h of thermal ageing at 85°C in nitrogen,
72 where BA stands for butylammonium.²² Moreover, Sutanto et al. showed that the 2D structure of
73 PEA₂PbI₄ deposited on top of a triple cation 3D perovskite film undergoes a dynamical
74 transformation upon thermal ageing at 50°C that causes a decrease in PCE of 2D/3D perovskite
75 solar cells after only 100 minutes of heating, reaching 97% of the initial PCE.²³

76 In this work, we study 3D perovskite films with a 2D layer of PEA₂PbI₄ on the top surface and
77 its evolution upon exposure to moisture, heat and continuous illumination. We reveal that a 2D
78 layer of PEA₂PbI₄ is formed uniquely on the top surface of triple-cation
79 (FA_{0.83}MA_{0.17})_{0.95}CS_{0.05}Pb(I_{0.83}Br_{0.17})₃-based 3D perovskite films. In contrast, when MAPbI₃-
80 based perovskite films are used - showing a lower PL quantum yield which we associate to a
81 higher defectivity of the thin film- not all PEAI self-assembles as PEA₂PbI₄ on the surface. Part
82 of the added PEAI diffuses through the bulk forming PEA₂PbI₄ phases within the bulk even
83 before thermal ageing. Such diffusion is observed on triple-cation
84 (FA_{0.83}MA_{0.17})_{0.95}CS_{0.05}Pb(I_{0.83}Br_{0.17})₃-based 3D perovskite films too when subjected to long-term
85 thermal stress and light soaking. We further show that the 2D perovskite capping layer quickly
86 disappears when the film is subjected to mild moisture and heat at the same time, allowing water
87 molecules to penetrate through the film and convert 3D halide perovskite into PbI₂.

88 **Experimental Section**

89 **Materials and Methods**

90 Lead (II) iodide (PbI_2 , 99.99%, CAS No. 10101-63-0), Lead (II) bromide (PbBr_2 , $\geq 98\%$) were
91 purchased from Tokyo Chemical Industry (TCI); Formamidinium iodide (FAI),
92 phenethylammonium iodide (PEAI) methylammonium bromine (MABr) and
93 methylammonium iodide (MAI) were purchased from Dyesol ; Cesium iodide (CsI) was
94 purchased from Alfa Aesar. N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF, anhydrous, 99.8%),
95 Chlorobenzene (anhydrous, 99.8%), dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, anhydrous, $\geq 99.9\%$) and
96 isopropyl alcohol (IPA), were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. All chemicals were used without
97 any further purification. Glass substrates were cleaned in an ultra bath sonicator with deionized
98 (DI) water plus 3% volume of Hellmanex III, DI water, acetone and IPA, for 10 minutes each
99 step. The so cleaned glass substrates were treated with oxygen plasma for 10 minutes just before
100 any further deposition. All samples were prepared inside the glovebox under controlled N_2
101 atmosphere.

102 Pristine MAPbI_3 thin film perovskites were prepared by spin coating a 1.2 M solution
103 (MAI: $\text{PbI}_2=1:1$) in DMSO:DMF (volume ratio 1:4) at 4000 rpm for 30 seconds. After 10
104 seconds, 150 μL of chlorobenzene was dropped on the spinning sample. The precursor solution
105 was left stirring overnight at room temperature prior the deposition. An hour before deposition
106 the temperature was raised to 50°C while the solution was left stirring. The sample was annealed
107 for 10 minutes at 100°C .

108 Pristine MAFACsPbI_3 thin film perovskites were prepared by spin coating a 1.3 M solution
109 (FAI:MABr: $\text{PbI}_2=0.79:0.16:1$) in DMSO:DMF (volume ratio 1:4) at 4000 rpm for 30 seconds. 6
110 seconds before the end of the program, 200 μL of chlorobenzene was dropped on the spinning
111 sample. The precursor solution was left stirring overnight at room temperature prior the
112 deposition. An hour before deposition 5 mol% CsI solution (1.5 M in DMSO) was added and the

113 temperature was raised to 50°C while the solution was left stirring. The sample was annealed for
114 1 hour at 100°C.

115 2D/3D multijunction was created by dynamically spin coating a PEAI solution (60 mmol in
116 anhydrous IPA) on top of the pre-crystallized perovskite thin film at 4000 rpm for 30 seconds.
117 The material was then post-annealed at 100°C for 5 minutes to allow evaporation of the solvent.
118 5% molar excess of PbI₂ in the MAPbI₃ (MAI:PbI₂=1:1.05) and CsFAMAPb(IBr)₃
119 (FAI:PbI₂=1:1.05) precursor solution was added to obtain more reproducible samples with
120 higher structural order of the 2D phases (Figure S1).

121 **Characterization**

122 *PL* spectra under thermal ageing were measured using the electro-luminescence module of Arkeo
123 all-in-one measurement platform (CicciResearch). The emission was measured using a fiber
124 coupled CCD spectrometer (300-1100 nm) upon single wavelength excitation (405 and 520 nm
125 depending on the material) in N₂ or atmospheric air. Samples were held at 85°C using a Peltier
126 based TEC module also under *PL* acquisition. Light soaking was provided by a white Illuminator
127 LED module calibrated at 1 sun intensity. *UV-Vis* absorption was measured on perovskite thin
128 films deposited on bare glass using a UV/VIS/NIR spectrophotometer Lambda 1050,
129 PerkinElmer, in the wavelength range 400–900 nm and with step size of 4 nm. *XRD* patterns
130 were recorded with a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer with Bragg–Brentano geometry
131 equipped with a Cu Kα1 ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) anode, operating at 40 kV and 40 mA. All the
132 diffraction patterns were collected at room temperature, with a step size of 0.05 in symmetric
133 scan reflection mode and an acquisition time of 1 s. Perovskite films were prepared on bare glass
134 substrates.

135 **Results and Discussion**

136 To get deeper insights into the stability of 2D perovskite capping layers on 3D bulks we explore
137 two 3D different compositions: single-cation MAPbI₃ and triple-cation
138 (FA_{0.83}MA_{0.17})_{0.95}Cs_{0.05}Pb(I_{0.83}Br_{0.17})₃ (hereafter defined as MAFACsPbI₃).

139 **Figure 1a** shows the photoluminescence (PL) spectra of pristine MAPbI₃ and MAFACsPbI₃,
140 respectively (not subjected to any passivation process). The PL intensity is normalized with
141 respect to the optical density measured at the excitation wavelength (520 nm) to assure equal
142 absorption of the films (UV-Visible absorbance are shown in Figure S2). The photoluminescence
143 of thin films is highly sensitive to defect density, which affects radiative and non-radiative
144 carrier decay paths.²⁴ The MAFACsPbI₃ perovskite film is about three times more emissive than
145 MAPbI₃, inferring reduced non-radiative recombination. These results are in good agreement
146 with previous works that attributed the role of cation mixing to the suppression of carrier
147 recombination pathways and increased thermodynamic stability.²⁵⁻²⁷ **Figure 1b** shows the X-ray
148 Diffraction (XRD) patterns for pristine MAPbI₃ and MAFACsPbI₃ thin films. Both materials
149 exhibit good crystallinity, with main diffraction peaks at 14°, 28° and 32° which correspond to
150 the (110), (220) and (310) phase, respectively, typical of the tetragonal perovskite phase.

Figure 1. **a** PL spectra of pristine MAPbI₃ and MAFACsPbI₃ thin films measured under single wavelength excitation of 520 nm in air (RH 65%). Spectra have been normalized with respect to the optical density of each film at the excitation wavelength. **b** XRD peaks of MAPbI₃ and MAFACsPbI₃. **c-d** Dynamical evolution of the PL spectrum of MAPbI₃ and MAFACsPbI₃ under thermal ageing at 85°C for 6 hours in air (RH 65%), respectively (CW 520 nm excitation).

151 To further assess the stability of pristine MAPbI₃ and MAFACsPbI₃ under thermal stress we
 152 monitored the PL spectra evolution while the samples were heated at 85°C for 6 hours in air, as
 153 shown in **Figure 1c-d**. The absolute intensity of MAPbI₃ 3D peak gradually decreases over 6
 154 hours of continuous exposure at 85°C. In contrast, the intensity of the 3D peak of MAFACsPbI₃
 155 maintained its initial value, confirming the enhanced thermal stability of mixed cation structures
 156 and reduced formation of trap states.^{28,29} Notably, when the PL spectra was monitored in air at

157 room temperature, both MAPbI₃ and MAFACsPbI₃ showed PL enhancement (Figure S3),
158 probably due to passivation of trap states by oxygen.³⁰ The photoluminescence results under
159 thermal stress were confirmed also when MAPbI₃ and MAFACsPbI₃ thin films were aged at
160 85°C in N₂ for 250 hours (Figure S4 and Figure S5). XRD patterns of MAPbI₃ and MAFACsPbI₃
161 were measured before and after thermal ageing (Figure S6 and Figure S7); The intensity of XRD
162 peaks associated to the 3D perovskite phase is reduced by 50% and 35% with respect to the
163 initial values, respectively, indicating a more severe loss in crystallinity for MAPbI₃ after
164 thermal ageing.

165 To create the multi-junction 2D/3D thin films, PEAI was dissolved in isopropyl alcohol (IPA)
166 and dynamically spin-coated on top of the 3D perovskite, which was deposited with 5 mol%
167 excess of PbI₂ to stabilize the interface.^{18,31,32} **Figure 2a** shows the XRD patterns of PEAI-treated
168 MAPbI₃ and MAFACsPbI₃ thin films after thermal annealing at 100°C for 10 minutes. XRD
169 peaks at 14°, 28° and 5.4° can be clearly distinguished, which correspond to the tetragonal
170 perovskite phase of the 3D bulk and, at lower angles, to the presence of PEAI. More specifically,
171 the peak at 5.4° corresponds to the formation of pure 2D PEA₂PbI₄ perovskite. Weak XRD peaks
172 at ~4.7° can be distinguished in both materials, which are consistent with the diffraction peak of
173 crystalline PEAI.¹² The formation of crystalline PEAI has been previously reported in the
174 literature and it was found to gradually convert to pure 2D perovskite phase during thermal
175 annealing,^{12,32} therefore, we expect the presence of PEAI to reduce as the heating time increases.

176

177 **Figure 2. a** XRD peaks of PEAI-treated MAPbI₃ and PEAI-treated MAFACsPbI₃ thin films after 10
 178 minutes post-annealing at 100°C. **b** PL spectra of PEAI-treated MAFACsPbI₃ and PEAI-treated MAPbI₃
 179 measured by exciting the material from the film-side. **c** PL spectra of PEAI-treated MAFACsPbI₃ and
 180 PEAI-treated MAPbI₃ measured by exciting the material from the glass-side.

181 **Figure 2b-c** show the PL spectra of PEAI-treated MAFACsPbI₃ and MAPbI₃ measured by
 182 exciting the material from the film and glass-side, respectively. When the PL spectra were
 183 recorded by exciting the materials from the film-side, the emission from the 2D capping layer
 184 was mainly detected. Both spectra show a clear emission at around 520 nm and a weaker peak at
 185 around 560 nm and MAFACsPbI₃ only shows a clear PL peak from the 3D bulk perovskite at
 186 760 nm. According to the literature, the bands appearing in the low-wavelength region

187 correspond to the emission of $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_{n-1}\text{Pb}_n\text{I}_{3n+1}$ with $n=1$ and $n=2$, respectively.^{23,33} These
188 results are in agreement with the XRD data showed in **Figure 2a**, where a preferential growth
189 orientation of the pure 2D PEA_2PbI_4 phase is observed (5.4°). PL peaks from
190 $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_{n-1}\text{Pb}_n\text{I}_{3n+1}$ onto MAFACsPbI_3 are blue-shifted with respect to the ones observed in
191 PEAI-treated MAPbI_3 , probably due to some I^- ions that have been replaced by Br^- ions.^{34,35}
192 **Figure 2c** shows that when the PL is measured by exciting the PEAI-treated MAFACsPbI_3 film
193 through the glass, only the peak centered at 760 nm is clearly distinguished and no PL emissions
194 in the low-wavelength region are observed, inferring that the 2D layer of PEA_2PbI_4 firmly stays
195 on the top surface, in agreement with many reports in the literature.^{13,32} In contrast, when the PL
196 spectrum of the PEAI-treated MAPbI_3 film was measured from the glass side, as shown in
197 **Figure 2c**, clear emission from the PEA_2PbI_4 was detected at 520 nm, suggesting that some of
198 the PEAI might have diffused through the 3D bulk. These results show that depending on the
199 structural stability, and probably the defectivity of the underneath 3D bulk, PEAI may diffuse
200 through the material forming quasi-2D structures close to the substrate's interface. The
201 thermodynamic stability of the perovskite film is enhanced in mixed-cation compositions rather
202 than single-cation ones due to easier deprotonation of MA.^{26,36} PEA^+ may interact more easily
203 with the PbI_6 octahedra in MAPbI_3 rather than MAFACsPbI_3 , due to weaker bonds between
204 MA^+ and the PbI_6 , causing less adhesion of PEA_2PbI_4 onto the surface and more facile diffusion
205 of PEAI through the film during thermal annealing at 100°C . Therefore, the robustness of the 2D
206 overlayer may depend not only on the bulky molecule used to create the 2D/3D interface as
207 previously reported,¹⁸ but also on the quality of the underlying 3D bulk perovskite.

208 Then we have investigated the evolution of the 2D/3D junction under thermal stress. **Figure 3a-b**
209 show the evolution of PL spectra of PEAI-treated MAPbI_3 and PEAI-treated MAFACsPbI_3 thin

210 films under thermal stress (85°C for 250 h, in N₂). Upon thermal exposure, the 2D and quasi-2D
211 PEA₂MA_{n-1}Pb_nI_{3n+1} phase of both MAPbI₃ and MAFACsPbI₃ samples do not show an
212 appreciable change of the emission peak position. The absolute intensity of the PEA₂PbI₄ (n=1)
213 PL peak formed onto MAFACsPbI₃ diminishes overtime, while the PL peak assigned to the 3D
214 bulk emission at 760 nm remains unaltered upon thermal exposure, as also observed in pristine
215 MAFACsPbI₃ (Figure S5). Sutanto et al. observed similar trends for PEAI 2D-3D triple cation
216 perovskites upon thermal ageing at 50°C for 6 hours. They suggest a dynamical structural
217 variation of the 2D layer upon thermal stress, which does not affect the underneath 3D
218 perovskite.²³ In contrast, the absolute intensity of the PEA₂PbI₄ (n=1) PL peak formed onto
219 MAPbI₃ shows an initial increase, followed by a subsequent decay. The segregation of PbI₂ as a
220 separate phase, consequence of thermal decomposition,³⁷ could explain the initial increase of the
221 2D PEA₂PbI₄ phase observed in PEAI-treated MAPbI₃ films due to a reaction of the unconverted
222 crystalline PEAI and unreacted PbI₂. Moreover, the PL peak associated to quasi-2D
223 PEA₂MA_{n-1}Pb_nI_{3n+1} phase with n=2 increases with heating time for both MAPbI₃ and
224 MAFACsPbI₃ samples, as shown in Figure S8 and Figure S9. To further study any variation
225 within the bulk, the PL of PEAI-treated MAPbI₃ and MAFACsPbI₃ films was measured by
226 exciting the material from the glass side before and after thermal ageing for 6 hours (Figure
227 S10). As previously shown, PEAI-treated MAPbI₃ shows a weak PL peak in the low wavelength
228 region already at time 0, which remains unaltered during thermal ageing. In contrast, the PL peak
229 at low-wavelength appears in the PEAI-treated MAFACsPbI₃ after 6 hours of thermal ageing at
230 85°C, suggesting that the large cations have diffused through the material forming quasi-2D
231 structures close to the substrate's interface. This is in agreement with the loss of PL intensity
232 from the 2D feature close to the thin film surface.

233

234 **Figure 3. a-b** PL spectra evolution of PEAI-treated MAPbI₃ and PEAI-treated MAFACsPbI₃ thin films
 235 upon thermal ageing at 85°C for 250 hours in N₂ (single wavelength excitation at 405 nm), respectively.
 236 **c-d** XRD peaks of PEAI-treated MAPbI₃ and PEAI-treated MAFACsPbI₃ thin films before and after
 237 thermal ageing at 85°C in N₂ for 250 hours, respectively.

238 In order to detect any structural change upon thermal exposure, we measured the XRD patterns
 239 before and after thermal ageing (85° for 250 h in N₂), which are shown in **Figure 3c-d**. Both
 240 materials initially showed a distinct peak at ~4.7° assigned to the crystalline PEAI form, which
 241 totally disappeared after thermal ageing. Upon thermal ageing a weak XRD peak at 4° assigned
 242 to the mixed 2D PEA₂MA_{n-1}Pb_nI_{3n+1} phase with n=2 appears, in agreement with PL results
 243 shown in **Figure 3a**. Most importantly, the intensity of XRD peaks typical of the 3D perovskite

244 phase (14° , 28° and 32°) decreases for both materials; i.e. the (110) peak at $\sim 14^\circ$ is reduced by
245 42% and 26% for 2D/MAPbI₃ and 2D/MAFACsPbI₃, respectively. The results suggest that the
246 2D capping is not stable when exposed to thermal stress and undergoes structural
247 transformations, which may lead to partial diffusion of the bulky molecule through the film. The
248 degradation of the underneath 3D bulk is slowed down but not completely avoided when the
249 material is subjected to long-term thermal ageing, i.e. the 3D perovskite phase diffraction signal
250 of 2D/MAFACsPbI₃ is reduced by 26% with respect to the initial value, while it decreases by
251 35% in pristine MAFACsPbI₃.

252 To assess whether the PEAI-based 2D capping layer can effectively protect the underneath bulk
253 from moisture, we have repeated the thermal ageing experiments for PEAI-treated MAFACsPbI₃
254 in air (85°C , 250 h, air 35 % Relative Humidity - RH). **Figure 4a** shows the PL spectra measured
255 for the material excited from the film-side before and after thermal exposure in air. The inset
256 image displays a magnification of the PL peak in the 650-900 nm range. PL peaks associated to
257 the pure PEA₂PbI₄ and quasi-2D phase completely disappear upon thermal ageing and the one
258 assigned to the 3D bulk at 760 nm is considerably reduced. Similarly, the XRD peak at low-
259 angles typical of the 2D PEA₂PbI₄ phase disappears (**Figure 4b**), while the intensity of the XRD
260 peaks assigned to the 3D perovskite structure decreases, leaving behind PbI₂ as decomposition
261 product as evidenced by the intense XRD peak at 12.5° , which corresponds to the 001 peak of
262 crystalline PbI₂. We previously showed that the presence of a 2D capping layer seems to retard
263 the thermal degradation of MAFACsPbI₃ when aged in N₂ at 85°C . However, the presence of
264 moisture accelerates the degradation of the 2D capping layer, with subsequent loss of the bulky
265 cation, failing in protecting the 3D bulk from thermal stress and allowing moisture to penetrate
266 through the material damaging it. Indeed similar degradation of a pristine MAFACsPbI₃ is

267 observed when aged under the same conditions (**Figure 4c**). Figure S11 shows the XRD patterns
 268 of MAPbI₃ and PEAI-treated MAPbI₃ films as deposited and after being aged at 85°C in air for
 269 250 h (RH 35%). Similarly to what observed for MAFACsPbI₃, the presence of moisture
 270 accelerates the degradation of the 2D/3D heterojunction, allowing water molecules to penetrate
 271 through the film and convert MAPbI₃ into PbI₂. The presence of the bulky cation in the 2D
 272 capping layer can act as barrier to prevent moisture uptake. However, prolonged exposure to
 273 moisture at high temperature (85°C) may cause both a simple diffusion of the large cation and/or
 274 the volatilization of PEA and HI, causing the hydration of the 3D perovskite underneath. Our
 275 results show that PEA₂PbI₄ is not sufficient in protecting the underlying 3D perovskite from
 276 moisture uptake and degradation when it is co-exposed to thermal stress.

277

278 **Figure 4. a** PL spectra of PEAI-treated MAFACsPbI₃ before and after thermal ageing at 85°C for 250
 279 hours in atmospheric air (RH 35%, CW 450 nm excitation). **b** XRD peaks of PEAI-treated MAFACsPbI₃
 280 before (bottom) and after (top) thermal ageing at 85°C for 250 hours in atmospheric air. **c** XRD peaks of
 281 pristine MAFACsPbI₃ before (bottom) and after (top) thermal ageing at 85°C for 250 hours in
 282 atmospheric air.

283 To further evaluate the stability variations upon PEAI addition in MAPbI₃ and MAFACsPbI₃
 284 thin film, we calculated the intensity proportion between the (001) peak of crystalline PbI₂ and
 285 (110) peak of the perovskite tetragonal phase before and after thermal ageing in air for 250 hours
 286 (Figure S12). The stability of MAFACsPbI₃ is slightly enhanced when the surface is treated with

287 PEAI, showing reduced conversion of halide perovskite into crystalline PbI_2 . In contrast, PEAI
288 on MAPbI_3 seems to negatively affect its stability, accelerating the degradation. This might be
289 due to its fast penetration through the bulk and damage of the $[\text{PbI}_6]^{4-}$ structure, with subsequent
290 acceleration of the 3D crystal structure disruption. Recently, Lei et al observed that excess of
291 PEAI addition in MAPbI_3 can indeed accelerate its degradation due to interaction between the
292 amino group of PEA^+ and the $[\text{PbI}_6]^{4-}$ octahedral, leading to the damage of the 3D crystal
293 structure.³⁸ Our results further support this observation, showing that the quality of the bulk of
294 the 3D perovskite underneath the 2D capping layer will define also the degradation rate of the
295 film.

296 Finally, the thermal ageing experiment for PEAI-treated MAFACsPbI_3 was repeated under
297 continuous illumination (85°C , 250 h, N_2 under simulated 1 sun illumination). **Figure 5a** shows
298 the PL spectra of a PEAI-treated MAFACsPbI_3 thin film before and after 250 hours of thermal
299 ageing under continuous simulated 1 sun illumination in N_2 . While the peak centered at about
300 760 nm assigned to the 3D bulk remains unchanged, the pure 2D PEA_2PbI_4 phase disappears
301 during the first 20 hours of ageing (see Figure S13), leaving behind a broad peak centered at
302 about 560 nm, which suggests the evolution of the pure 2D phase into mixed $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_{n-1}\text{Pb}_n\text{I}_{3n+1}$
303 phases. Interestingly, such dynamical evolution of the 2D/3D multi junction was not observed
304 when the film was thermally annealed in the dark (see **Figure 3a**). The XRD measurements
305 shown in **Figure 5b** confirm the absence of pure 2D PEA_2PbI_4 phase after 250 hours of ageing at
306 85°C , in N_2 under illumination and unaltered crystallinity of the underneath 3D bulk. Figure S14
307 shows the PL spectra of the PEAI-treated MAFACsPbI_3 film measured from the glass side after
308 thermal ageing at 85°C under continuous illumination (patterns plotted in logarithmic scale). We
309 noticed the appearance of a peak at about 550 nm, indicating the formation of mixed

310 $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_{n-1}\text{Pb}_n\text{I}_{3n+1}$ phases near the glass substrate. These results suggest that even
 311 MAFACs PbI_3 films, structurally more stable and with a better optoelectronic quality, show the
 312 diffusion of PEA I through the 3D bulk under light soaking and thermal stress, which might have
 313 some implications on the stability of the material if further stressed. Similar dynamical evolution
 314 of the 2D/3D MAFACs PbI_3 interface was observed when films were aged at room temperature
 315 (25°C), in N_2 under illumination (Figure S15 and Figure S16), showing that the dynamical
 316 structural variation of the 2D/3D multi-junction occurs in the presence of light, and is accelerated
 317 by temperature. Light induced degradation of the PEA_2PbI_4 capping layer may be due to a slow
 318 and partial volatilization of PEA and HI within the 250 hours of illumination, which are released
 319 from the surface, leaving PbI_2 residue as previously reported by Fang et al.³⁹ for PEA_2PbI_4
 320 flakes. 2D perovskites suffer for the presence of defects and light instability – even more than 3D
 321 systems. Thus here we learn that also in the form of 2D/3D heterojunction they still retain most
 322 of the weaknesses identified for pure 2D thin films, flakes or single crystals.

323

324 **Figure 5. a** PL spectra of PEA I -treated MAFACs PbI_3 before and after thermal ageing at 85°C for 250
 325 hours in N_2 under continuous simulated 1 sun illumination (CW 405 nm excitation). **b** XRD peaks of
 326 PEA I -treated MAFACs PbI_3 before (bottom) and after (top) thermal ageing at 85°C for 250 hours N_2
 327 under continuous simulated 1 sun illumination.

328 To conclude, we studied the 2D/3D multi-junction formation by depositing PEAI in IPA on top
329 of MAPbI₃ and MAFACsPbI₃. 2D PEA₂PbI₄ capping layers are formed on the surface of both
330 3D bulk perovskites. The capping layer firmly adheres on the surface of MAFACsPbI₃.
331 However, part of the PEAI might diffuse through the 3D bulk when subjected to thermal ageing
332 at 85°C in N₂ for 250 h, failing in protecting the underneath 3D bulk from degradation and
333 causing loss in crystallinity. In contrast, PEAI partly diffuses through the bulk of MAPbI₃ even
334 before the film is subjected to thermal stress, probably due to its higher defectivity. We also
335 show that the 2D capping layer degrades when the same thermal ageing test is performed in air at
336 85°C and the underneath 3D bulk irreversibly converts to PbI₂, irrespectively of the 3D bulk
337 composition. Finally, we found that the 2D capping layer undergoes a structural evolution from
338 pure to mixed 2D phase when the film is aged under simulated 1 sun illumination. Such
339 structural evolution is accelerated when light soaking is combined with high temperature. Our
340 results show that light soaking induces major dynamical structural changes of the 2D capping
341 layer; this process is accelerated by temperature, strengthening the importance of evaluating the
342 stability of PSCs under continuous illumination and at high temperatures in order to evaluate its
343 proper implementation in a working device.

344 **Supporting Information**

345 Additional figures, including UV-Vis absorption spectra, PL spectra evolution during 250 hours
346 thermal ageing, XRD patterns before and after thermal ageing and peak intensity study.

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